

P.O. Box 2617,

Teheran.

10. 3. 71.

Dear Andrew,

I am sending this letter with Peter rather than send you verbal messenger alone.

Unfortunately your telegram only reached the Institute after David Whitehouse had left. But I was able to speak with Sarah Jennings, Peter Donaldson and others about the proposed removal of your pottery from Siraf to Shiraz. We all agreed that the problems presented by police checks along the road (the factor that dissuaded us from sending your Teheran material to Shiraz) would be even more acute between Siraf and Shiraz without official papers saying that all was in order. ^{Because of} smuggling checks _{etc}

Peter Faries suggested that your friendly relations with the chief of Police in Bushire (I think it was Bushire) might

allow you to get official papers that would authorize the removal, and subsequent movement, of the pottery.

If you think this is quite likely yourself, by all means give it a try. But I would be surprised if he were willing to stick his neck out on this issue - just as I ^{reluctant} think David Whitehouse might have been also.

The chief point in any case is that I do not consider it worthwhile either from your point of view, the local dig's point of view, or the Institute's point of view to attempt to move the pottery from Sinal to Shiraz if you do not get the necessary papers to cover such an action from the local police and/or customs.

I am sure Sir Max would agree with this.

~~It is~~ I would rather not seek permission from the Museum either, since this might be complicated & they might even refuse - or start demanding a division of the material etc.

If you can do nothing now all will not

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be lost. You can still work on the material in the late afternoon when the dig is on again (and have what you wish kept sent up at the end of the season).

If you can come to Rehman soon I would be glad on another count. After discussions with Charles + H.E. I decided that it would be better to hold your permit application re the Islands. Basil Gray agreed with this too. If you can come up and we can have another general discussion here we can push your permit in, either in its present form or perhaps, if others suggest such a course, less some of the islands mentioned.

Hoping to see you fairly soon - and that you and Martha are both well. Sorry so ~~many~~ ^{many} sounds of caution but I am also thinking of you as well as the rest.

Yours,
David